

ON THE STUDY OF THE DEHYDRATION OF SOME PURE AND MIXED CHROMI-SELENIC ALUMS AND THE FORMATION OF CORRESPONDING COMPLEX CHROMI-SELENATES.

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The changes of properties of some pure and mixed chromi-selenic alums with rise of temperature have been studied. In the vacuum desiccators and in the room temperature, different hydrates are formed. But at higher temperatures up to 160°, the violet alums are converted into green complex chromi-selenates in which the Cr, SeO₄, and SO₄ ions are absent.

The properties of the chromo-sulphuric alums at higher temperatures have been studied by many investigators (Müller-Erzbach, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1888, 2, 113; Lescoeur and Mathurin, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1888, 50, 33; Lowel, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1855, iii, 44, 320).

At the ordinary temperatures chromo-alums over concentrated H₂SO₄ lose six molecules of water. Above 80° to 90° further molecules of water are eliminated accompanied by change of colour from violet to green. At higher temperatures, anhydrous products are also obtained. Using the Tensi-eudiometric method of Huttig (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1920, 114, 162; 1922, 121, 245; 1922, 122, 46; 1923, 126, 168), Krauss, Fricke and Queren-gasser (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1929, 181, 38) found potassium chromium alum to exist above 21° as a dodecahydrate. At 95° it again changed into tetrahydrate and became anhydrous above 408°, whereas the corresponding aluminium salt existed as 6-, 4-, 2-, and 0- hydrates at temperatures above 47°, 80°, 120° and 240° respectively.

Fabre prepared chromo-selenic alums by mixing violet chromium selenate with selenates of Na, K, Rb, Cs, Tl, etc. (*Compt. rend.*, 1887, 106). The alums form very distinct octahedra. They are violet-red by transmitted light and their solutions are violet when cold but at 55°-60° become green. The solutions crystallise only when allowed to evaporate spontaneously for several months. The selenic alums are more soluble than the corresponding sulphuric alums. Gerichten (*Ber.*, 1873, 6, 162) also prepared many chromi-selenic alums. Recently Sarkar and Bhattacharyya prepared a mixed chromo-selenic alum which formed violet octahedral crystals (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 765).

In this paper, the changes of properties of the following alums with rise of temperature have been studied. The alums were prepared according to the methods given in the respective papers.

- I. $\text{Cr}_2 (\text{SeO}_4)_3 \cdot (\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{SeO}_4, 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$.
 II. $\text{Cr}_2 (\text{SeO}_4)_3 \cdot (\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{SO}_4, 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$.
 III. $\text{Cr}_2 (\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot (\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{SeO}_4, 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$.
 IV. $\text{Cr}_2 (\text{SeO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4, 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Gerichten, *loc. cit.*).
 V. $\text{Cr}_2 (\text{SeO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{Na}_2 \text{SeO}_4, 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fabre, *loc. cit.*).
 VI. $\text{Cr}_2 (\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{Na}_2 \text{SeO}_4, 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Sarkar and Bhattacharyya, *loc. cit.*).

Since the selenates are decomposed at higher temperatures, the anhydrous products could not be obtained as in the case of the chromo-sulphuric alums. But at the room temperature (26° - 27°) and in the vacuum desiccator the hydrates with 11, 11, 12, 12, 10 and 11 H_2O respectively were obtained from the above mentioned alums.

The following is a list of the complex hydrates described for the first time in this paper.

- (A) $(\text{NH}_4)_2 [\text{Cr}(\text{SeO}_4)_2], 2 \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$.
 (B) $(\text{NH}_4)_2 \left[\text{Cr} \begin{array}{c} (\text{SeO}_4)_3 \\ (\text{SO}_4) \end{array} \right], 3 \text{H}_2\text{O} \text{ and } 1 \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$.
 (C) $(\text{NH}_4)_2 \left[\text{Cr} \begin{array}{c} (\text{SeO}_4) \\ (\text{SO}_4)_3 \end{array} \right], 4\text{H}_2\text{O}, 3 \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}, 3 \text{H}_2\text{O} \text{ and } 2 \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$.
 (D) $\text{Na}_2 [\text{Cr}(\text{SeO}_4)_2], 2\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{H}_2\text{O} \text{ and } 0 \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$.
 (E) $\text{Na}_2 \left[\text{Cr} \begin{array}{c} (\text{SeO}_4) \\ (\text{SO}_4)_3 \end{array} \right], 4 \text{H}_2\text{O}, 3\text{H}_2\text{O} \text{ and } 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Known weights of the violet alums were left in desiccators over H_2SO_4 and after two or three days, they were found to lose in weight which was due to loss of water. The partially dehydrated salt was then left in a vacuum desiccator, when there was no loss in weight even after 48 hours.

The colour of the alums remained violet; Cr, SeO_4 or SO_4 ions could be detected in aqueous solutions.

The alums were then heated in a regulated air thermostat at various temperatures for many hours and the loss in weight determined for each temperature. The results of dehydration of the salts studied in this paper are shown in Table I. The results are shown in the curves (Figs. 1-3).

TABLE I.
Dehydration temperatures.

	26° vacuum	80°	85°	90°	100°	105°	110°	120°	130°	140°	150°	160°
Salt I	20·3	20·98	20·98	22·2	26·7	29·0	30·3	32·3	30·3	32·3	30·3	30·3
Salt II	20·7	33·1	33·1	34·3	34·3	34·3	36·97	36·97	36·97	36·97	36·97	36·97
Salt III	22·1	35·9	36·5	36·5	36·5	36·5	37·1	37·1	37·7	37·7	38·5	38·5
Salt IV	19·09	31·5	31·9	31·9	31·9	31·9	32·9	32·9	33·6	35·5	35·5	35·5
Salt V	21·6	33·5	34·2	34·2	34·2	34·2	35·5	35·5	36·2	36·8	36·8	36·8
Salt VI	22·2	36·1	36·1	37·2	37·2	37·2	38·1	39·1	39·1	39·1	39·1	39·1

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

DISCUSSION.

In the case of salt I, 19 molecules of water were eliminated between 80° and 110°. The violet alum turned perfectly green and when dissolved in ice-cold water formed a green solution in which both Cr and SeO_4 ions were not detected. But if the solution was heated, the complex decomposed. As there was no loss in weight from 110° to 160°, a new complex (A), stable between large range of temperatures, was formed.

Between 90° and 105°, 21 molecules of water were removed from the salt II and green hygroscopic powder was obtained. The salt formed with water a green solution in which Cr, SeO_4 and SO_4 ions were absent in the cold. So a definite complex hydrate with 3 H_2O was formed. After removal of 22.5 molecules of water at 110°, the green product obtained was sparingly soluble in water forming a green solution in which the Cr, SeO_4 and SO_4 ions were absent. Thus another definite complex hydrate (B) with 1.5 molecules of water and stable up to 160° was obtained.

On heating, the salt III was converted into four different hydrates of a complex (C) with 4, 3.5, 3 and 2.5 molecules of H_2O , with stability range of 80°-100°, 110°-120°, 130°-150°, 150°-180° respectively. Cr, SO_4 , and SeO_4 ions were absent in the complex in the cold.

The Salt IV, was, on heating, converted into three definite perfectly green complex hydrates, having 4, 3 and 1.5 molecules of water, stable between the temperatures 80° and 100°; 100° and 120°; 130° and 160° and having the composition

The three definite complex hydrates (D) having 2, 1 or 0.5 molecules of water were produced from the salt V. Cr and SeO_4 ions were absent in the cold.

FIG. 3.

Dehydration curves of salts IV, V & VI.

The salt VI on heating formed a hygroscopic powder. The green aqueous solution gave no test for Cr, SeO_4 and SO_4 ions. Thus three definite complex hydrates (E) having 4, 3 or 2 molecules of water and stable between 80° and 85° , 90° and 100° and 120° and 160° were obtained.

All these 16 compounds were definite green coloured hydrates as was shown by their stability between large ranges of temperatures. They were all complexes; Cr, SeO_4 or SO_4 ions were not identified in freshly prepared cold aqueous solutions. They were not, however, stable being decomposed on standing or on heating.

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